

“It’s our only connection”: Mobile phones and romantic relationships in India

Carolyn Wei – Google, User Experience Research, Kirkland, WA, USA, +1 (425) 739-5869, weicar@google.com

Abstract

This paper reports on a field study of mobile phone use in romantic relationships. This multi-method study included a questionnaire, interview, mobile phone use diary, and participant observation. The 20 participants, aged 18-30, were sampled primarily from a 24-hour technology support centre in Bangalore, India. We found that many of the participants depended on their mobile phones to facilitate connections with loved ones from whom they were separated geographically or culturally. Consequently, participants developed mobile phone behaviours that simulated face-to-face habits such as waking loved ones up or saying goodnight at bedtime. The findings suggest that the mobile phone is an emotional tool for nurturing romantic relationships and supporting users’ desires to occupy multiple symbolic spaces. Results are interpreted through the theoretical lens of hybridity and cyborgs, a framework that explains how mobile phone use is imbued with emotion and how users develop new lifestyles and connections with their phones.

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Introduction

This paper reports on young, urban, middle-class people who use mobile phones to support romantic relationships in Bangalore, India. The local culture of Bangalore is a heterogeneous mixture and fusion that reflects the influences of historical ethnic populations, former colonizers, migration of workers to cities, transnational networks, global media messages, and international products and services like Coca-Cola and McDonalds. Besides being post-colonial, India is digitally emergent—a place that is in the midst of developing pervasive, digital telecommunication and media infrastructure. It is rapidly developing economically and technologically with high tech, modern cities situated beside agrarian areas with no telephone system at all.

Studying intimate personal relationships is especially enlightening in settings like Bangalore, which is still socially conservative even as it experiences swift “modernization.” The close connection that a person may have with his or her mobile phone, combined with the structured nature of dating and courtship in traditional societies, creates a powerful opportunity to observe how technology supports intimate personal relationships. This paper considers how new technologies support time-honoured rituals and behaviours and are adopted for romantic relationships.

The process of adopting mobile technology may conflict with traditional patterns or values, for example, when mobiles allow teenagers to circumvent parental controls in their romantic choices. In that scenario, the mobile is facilitating an age-old compulsion rather than creating a previously unknown desire. However, some of the behaviours that arise are as hybrid as the cultures under observation and reflect a merger of the old and contemporary, and the local and the global, such as making mobile phones a virtual leash that lets teenagers roam away from home under the supervision of parents, or as a means for a young person to get to know a potential spouse who lives overseas and who has already been vetted and approved by parents. Such behaviours with mobile phones give new expression to old impulses as well as those that are hybrids of existing customs that suit the evolving cultural environments of Bangalore. These behaviours are characterized by a new theory of mobile hybridity that articulates how mobile phones are a tool that helps users navigate the cultural flows of a hybrid world.

The purpose of the study reported here was to understand how young people in Bangalore use information and communication technology, especially mobile phones, to support their romantic relationships in a culturally blended space. The study examines how mobile phones are used as part of a “communications repertoire” (Haddon & Vincent, 2005) for supporting the various

stages of a romantic relationship such as finding a partner, courtship, engagement, and marriage. This paper reviews the relevant theoretical and empirical literature and then describes the methods of the multi-method field study that was conducted. Selected results are presented and discussed.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

This paper is framed by “hybridity,” a concept rooted in post-colonial studies and globalization. In this project, hybridity is an umbrella term that refers to liminal spaces, cosmopolitan worlds (Appadurai, 1996), and borderlands (Anzaldúa, 1999). Hybridity is a way to understand the people who occupy such spaces and the synthetic blending of elements of their identity and behaviour that occurs as multiple cultures come into contact and influence them. These cultural mixtures are a crucial “third space” that the polar cultures react to and interact in (Bhabha, 1994). People rely on this space for their identity, one that prevents them from having to choose between a “primordial polarity,” be it traditional or modern, local or global, or dutiful child or independent adult. This concept of hybridity is a useful lens for examining digitally emergent, post-colonial sites, the people who occupy such spaces, and the way that they use the mobile phone.

Hybridity creates an avenue into a discussion of cyborg theory, a body of work that concerns the close integration of people with everyday technology. In this paper, “cyborg” broadly refers to how users seamlessly assimilate tools into their routine habits to construct their identity in complex circumstances, a concept framed by Haraway (1991) to describe feminist constructions of identity and also adopted by Hayles (1999) to characterize “post-human” embodied communication. The “natural-born cyborgs” described by Clark (2003) smoothly integrate everyday technologies that change their way of thinking. For example, people who wear wristwatches usually say they know the time when asked, even before they have checked their watch. The awareness that the wristwatch is available is enough for users to consider the time as something within their domain of ready knowledge. Besides explaining the ease with which people have taken to mobile phones, cyborg theory is a lens through which to understand how users construct new, hybrid identities with their mobile phone in order to navigate the multiple spheres that they occupy, especially spheres that may seem disjointed, such as parents’ values versus individual desires, or Indian culture versus global culture.

In addition to hybridity and cyborg theories, theories of perpetual contact and mobile phones inform this paper. The ready availability of the mobile phone allows family and friends always to be available. This phenomenon of being constantly connected and plugged into a social network has been labelled in different ways, each with its own nuance including “absent presence” (Gergen, 2002), “connected presence” (Licoppe, 2004), and “perpetual contact” (Katz & Aakhus, 2002). This perpetual contact speaks to occupation of a shared “inside space” (Gergen, 2002) in a mobile call and a closeness to others that transcends physical distance.

Romantic uses of mobile phones

Some research has already identified links between romance and mobile phones. The intimate fit of the mobile phone with the hand and its constant presence with the user make it an apt symbol for romantic feelings. Also, users imbue their mobile phones with feelings that reflect the value of the information exchange and communication with loved ones that they have on them (Vincent, 2003).

Most mobile phone use that supports romantic relationships organically extends pre-mobile behaviours. For example, teenagers exchange daily good-morning and good-night text messages with their sweethearts, a briefer, more frequent evolution of the good-night chat that might have occurred on fixed-line telephones in an earlier era (Kasesniemi & Rautiainen, 2002; Taylor & Harper, 2003). This affinity with previous fixed-line behaviour helps to integrate the mobile phone into the communications repertoire of a romantic relationship.

Once initiated, romantic relationships continue to be supported through mobile phones. Increased physical distance between a couple makes perpetual contact feel more urgent: the phone creates a perception of constant connection, and reachability becomes an important factor (Dietmar, 2005). Phone use also can reflect the state of a relationship, with women having comfortable telephone conversations with men with whom they have a good relationship, and women in uncertain relationships agonizing over when they should call (Sarch, 1993). Mobile phones can also work against a romantic relationship by facilitating cheating and deception, with entire affairs being conducted through flirty text messages and furtive phone calls (Ellwood-Clayton, 2006b).

The closeness that one feels with a mobile phone can help intimate relationships to blossom, like the phenomenon of textmates in the Philippines, which can accompany an embodied romance or be completely virtual (Ellwood-Clayton, 2006a). Such text relationships can become intimate quickly, where users share confidences or engage in “sex text” (Pertierra, 2005). In other words,

the mobile phone dovetails well with the work of romance, allowing people to closely connect with loved ones whom they know in the flesh as well as those people whom they know as digital constructions. Users keep their mobile close and use it as a medium for sharing the most personal parts of themselves with their loved one.

Methods

This research study was conducted in summer 2006 with a multimethod qualitative approach. A questionnaire and interview were used to gather data about the participants' attitudes and self-descriptions of their social practices and relationships with family, friends, and loved ones. That information was confirmed or problematized during participant observation and debriefing over the mobile diary, which were based on actual phone use. The mobile diary, where participants described the calls and texts that they made and received, was informed by the log used by Grinter and Eldridge (2001) in their study of English teenagers and their SMS patterns. The diary was intended to prompt participants to share stories about actual incidents of use with the researcher (Wei, 2007). At the end of the study, all participants were given gift certificates worth 200 INR (approx. 5 USD) redeemable at Café Coffee Day, a national chain.

Twenty young, urban, middle-class people in Bangalore were recruited for this study. This population was targeted because it is likely to use mobile technologies and to be exposed to multiple cultural forces in that cosmopolitan city. Participants were primarily recruited with an email announcement to workers at a technology support centre in Bangalore. These workers provide advanced technical support to customers worldwide around the clock. They are representative of the booming IT sector and offshoring industry in Bangalore that supports international companies at all hours.

Sixteen participants were men, and four were women. The gender imbalance represented the predominantly male population of the technology support centre. The median age of participants was 25. Four participants were married, two engaged, five in a steady committed relationship, one in an on-again, off-again relationship, and eight were single. With the exception of two pairs, the participants represented just "one side" of the relationship, e.g., their partners were not involved in the study. None of the participants was divorced or widowed. All of the participants were in heterosexual relationships. Participants were from all over India, and they were linguistically diverse. All spoke English professionally, so no interpreters or translators were used for this project.

Results and Discussion

Participants sometimes had romantic relationships that spanned continents. One participant, Shalini, met her future husband while playing an online game; she in Bangalore, and he in Saudi Arabia. After their wedding in Bangalore, her husband returned to work in Saudi Arabia, and she remained in Bangalore, living alone with her mother-in-law for over half a year. Now living together, she and her husband still keep in touch throughout the day over the computer and phone although they regularly see each other at home. Shalini is a woman living in the midst of modernity, working in high-tech, and at the same time, coping with traditional situations such as living with her mother-in-law. The technology in her life must work in concert with cultural contexts in order to support her relationships.

Mobile phones are used to maintain long-distance relationships and coordinate the instrumental needs of co-located relationships. Simultaneously, mobile phone communication symbolizes some of the changing practices related to marriage that are caused by global cultural flows. Also, mobile phones can circumvent cultural traditions. For example, Ambar and Nikhil were able to nurture their relationship somewhat below parental radar via daily phone calls sometimes lasting four to five hours a night.

Mobile phones can reinforce traditions as well. Prakash will have a traditional arranged marriage to a woman selected by his parents. However, his courtship has been conducted almost exclusively through mobile phone conversations: he has spent only two days in person with his fiancée, who lives over 2,000 km away in another city.

A characteristic shared by the relationships in this study is distance: six of the relationships including one of the marriages were long-distance. However, even the three co-located relationships have elements of distance: Shalini's marriage was facilitated over the internet; Nikhil had left Ambar behind in Nagpur when he was job hunting in Bangalore; and Kiran and Maya are separated by scheduling and parental issues. The mobile phone and computer-mediated communication are critical tools for closing distance (physical or otherwise) for such relationships. Nitin has only lived with his wife about 20 days in their half year of marriage because his wife is away studying for her degree. For them, the mobile phone is a vital link, "a god-sent gift; it has held us together."

The couple with the greatest physical distance between them may in fact be among the closest. Vijay's fiancée is currently working in the U.S. He works overnight in Bangalore, and she works during the day, so they work and sleep at about the same time. Their matched schedules

allow them to communicate two hours a day via chat, Web cam, or mobile phone calls, which is probably the most communication experienced by any physically separated couple in this study. Space and time intertwine to affect communication in a relationship, where time may make distance less acute.

Gaps more problematic than space are also addressed by mobile phones. Kiran and Maya, who are experiencing some disapproval from his parents, cannot spend much time together. Before his parents came to live with him, Kiran and Maya would meet daily. The mobile phone, Kiran said, was only used for coordinating. But now, the mobile phone has become an increasingly vital connection between the two of them, allowing them to exchange messages or chat for a few minutes. The mobile component in their relationship evolved from coordination device to meaningful communication. Judicious mobile phone use helps this couple to spend time together despite parental objections.

Mobile phone communication also holds together relationships that may otherwise have been torn apart by social pressures. Praveen's girlfriend is Christian while he is Hindu, so both their families object. His parents, he says, warn him that converting to Christianity will cut the couple off from his relatives. The distance between the couple and their religious differences has made the mobile a necessary tool. Within the "inside space" of the mobile conversation, the couple have a private space where they can be together free from any social pressures. In that mobile space, they do not have religious differences or concerned parents: they can just be themselves, a constructed, partial identity without problems. This relationship may be held together by virtue of the phone even though it may never be socially comfortable for the couple to be married.

Couples often create routines of fixed calling habits, which in many ways re-create the closeness and synchronization that might have occurred in face-to-face presence. For example, Raman described the routine he shares with his girlfriend over the mobile phone: They talk when he goes home in the evening. He wakes her up in the morning. She chats with him on the way to work on the bus. The mobile phone has increased intimacy for them because they could not have so much contact without it, especially separated in two cities. Its constant presence affords them a perpetual contact. Co-located couples can also develop similar customs. Nikhil and Ambar use the mobile as a way to do things "together" yet separately, such as when they go shopping but each want to look at their own things. The mobile allows them to connect and reconvene seamlessly when they are shopping. Perpetual contact makes shopping feel like a shared experience even when done separately.

The mobile phone can be used to express emotions implicitly, apart from verbalizing some sentiment. Rohit had smashed his phone after a fight with his girlfriend, making the phone a convenient physical outlet for his anger. Mobile phones can also be subtle sites for emotional expression. Vijay detailed through his mobile diary a quarrel over SMS with his fiancée over her calls bothering him at work. He told her later he would not talk with her for an entire month to make his point, though he admitted he might call her sooner if he missed her. Turning the phone off is the digital equivalent of giving someone the cold shoulder. By closing off this important communication channel with his fiancée, Vijay was strongly expressing his displeasure.

Mobiles themselves can also represent close connections, a perpetual contact with a loved one. Nikhil says his mobile phone is “an addiction. If I forget it, I think about it, I get scared. My wife’s not connected with me. It’s our only connection: I worry when the battery is low.” On the surface, Nikhil’s comment suggests a dependence on the mobile device itself, but on a deeper level, it is the connection to his wife that he is “addicted” to. The mobile phone enables a closeness that users enjoy and come to need—becoming cyborg as much with the affordance of connected presence as with the superficial connection of the device to their person.

Taken together, these results suggest that mobile phones are used in particular ways to support romantic relationships. Phones offer most utility for relationships that are experiencing challenges of distance, whether they are cultural gaps or physical separation. While problematic or long-distance relationships have long existed, mobile phones may make such relationships more sustainable (for better or worse) by bandaging problems of distance or social disapproval. The personal and portable nature of the mobile muffles secretive relationships from families or allows a couple that cannot overcome parental objections to stay in an indefinite holding pattern. Given that participants’ romantic relationships are complex and evolving, and that their attitudes about marriage are evolving along with changing social norms, the mobile phone is a core tool for bridging gaps and supporting relationships that do not fit neatly into a model of co-located and family-approved.

Conclusion

Mobiles are an indispensable technology that is intimately integrated into the habits of life. The perpetual contact afforded with social networks changes the way users think about themselves and their relationship with others. The constant presence of the phone creates a feeling of closeness with far away loved ones. But the resulting changes in behaviour are not always positive or easy. Perpetual contact has made mobile phones feel demanding. Some problematic

relationships (such as interreligious ones) remain intact with the aid of mobile phones despite enormous cultural and social pressures against them.

In this study, participants did not uproot cultural paradigms related to romance. They refined already present behaviours, such as dating, into new forms with their mobile communication. On the surface, participants who pursued relationships contrary to parental wishes appeared to be breaking norms. But when examined more closely, these relationships are actually naturalized into traditional cultural models, such as getting parental approval (with as much negotiation as necessary) before marriage or hiding the relationship to avoid dissent.

Mobile hybridity explains how mobile communication supports intimate relationships in a way that is both familiar and novel. Mobile phones are used to support romantic relationships in a way that feels natural. The participants' use of mobile phones organically stemmed from common impulses such as wanting to spend time with a romantic partner, even while separated. The cyborg relationship with mobile phones combined with perpetual contact allowed users to have their loved ones on hand at all times. This feeling of closeness despite physical gaps makes mobile support for distance relationships compelling for users.

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